

DEVELOPMENT OF OSTEOCHONDRITIS DISSECANS PATHOLOGY IN CONTEMPORARY CERVID POPULATIONS (*CERVUS ELAPHUS*, *CAPREOLUS CAPREOLUS*): A REFERENCE TOOL FOR ARCHAEOZOOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

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*To provide new reference points to study paleopathologies, this work has established a current reference of the affection produced on bone tissue by osteochondritis in wild populations of cervids (*Cervus elaphus* and *Capreolus capreolus*) using the astragalus. This condition has been related in several publications to the physical stress suffered by the animal, a characteristic that allows it to be linked to mobility patterns. The availability of this referential allows comparative studies to be carried out with archaeological materials, and it's the first time that systematic data on this type of injury has been published for red and roe deer.*

Archaeozoology, biomechanics, animal mobility patterns, paleopathology, osteochondritis, herd management

*Con el propósito de aportar nuevos referenciales para el estudio de las paleopatologías óseas en arqueozoología, se ha establecido mediante este trabajo un referencial actual de la afectación producida sobre el tejido óseo por la osteocondritis en poblaciones salvajes de cérvidos (*Cervus elaphus* y *Capreolus capreolus*) utilizando el astrágalo. Esta afectación se ha relacionado en varias publicaciones con el estrés físico sufrido por el animal, característica que permite vincularla a las pautas de movilidad animal. Disponer de este referencial permitirá la realización de estudios comparativos con materiales arqueológicos, tratándose de la primera vez que se publican datos sistemáticos sobre este tipo de lesión*

Paleopatología, movilidad, osteochondritis, zooarqueología, biomecánica, rebaño

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INTRODUCTION

Within the archaeozoological discipline, studies based on the analysis of bone palaeopathologies as a source of information on the living conditions and use of animal populations in the past are becoming increasingly important and numerous (Bendrey 2014: 258-65). In the case of wild animal populations, bone tissue affection and lesions provide information about health condition and traumatism suffered along the animal's life. In domestic animal populations, it's possible to record new lesions related to captivity and to the use of animal energy as a means of work (transport, traction...). The establishment of domestic herds led to a greater degree of territorial permanence and the exploitation of new resources, such as milk and animal power. These

changes had an impact on the reproduction and activity patterns of the animals and on their feeding. Biologically, the most important modifications experimented by the animals under these new pressures affected physiology, physical aspects, reproductive behavior, mobility, territoriality, and general activity patterns (Chang/Koster 1986: 97-148). One of the main elements of this new situation were related to the limited mobility of the animals and herds (versus the wild populations), leading finally to the extreme situation of stabling. The study of breeding conditions and patterns of animal mobility and activity in the past is therefore feasible on the basis of the analysis of biomechanically based bone damage (Sick/Kohut 2022: 52-70). So far, the studies of this topic are sparse but with interesting results showing the great potential of this approach for the analysis of the

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physical stress suffered by these animals. Concretely, the condition known as *osteocondritis dissecans* has been selected for this reference, as several studies have linked this condition to animal activity patterns and mobility (Sewell 2010: 1-60; Zimmermann *et al.* 2018: 13-27). The *osteocondrosis* is an articular pathology which develops during the period of animal's growth. It represents a common disorder that conditions the growth of the cartilaginous and bone tissue in animals, as well as in humans, called endochondral ossification. The lack of blood supply in certain areas of the bone causes a weak point in the cartilage, which can even become necrotic. As the affected individual grows, cartilage development is reduced. This causes advancement of ossification into the articular cartilage, resulting in a thinner cartilage growth layer (Ytrehus *et al.* 2007: 429-448). It is a pathology that is mainly found in the joints of the extremities (Nakano *et al.* 1987: 883-901; Van Weeren 2006: 248-258; Ytrehus *et al.* 2007: 429-448; McCoy *et al.* 2013: 1638-1647). Nevertheless, it may also arise affecting other joint surfaces like the back, hips, vertebrae or ribs (Nakano *et al.* 1987: 883-901; Ytrehus *et al.* 2007: 429-448). The condition can be identified in the bones because it appears in the early stages as an indentation on the articular surface and as a depression that may be porous in the later stages (Sewell 2010: 1-60). This pathology has been studied in different species like pigs, humans, bulls, horses, sheep, goats, dogs, turkeys and other domestic birds (Ytrehus *et al.* 2007: 429-448; McCoy *et al.* 2013: 1638-1647). Among scientists it is acknowledged to be a pathology produced by multiple causes mostly related to genetic conditions, physical strain, malnutrition and parasitic infections (Nakano *et al.* 1987: 883-901; Ytrehus *et al.* 2007: 429-448; McCoy *et al.* 2013: 1638-1647). This pathology can recover if there is no physical stress (Van Weeren/Brama 2003: 83-87). But it can also, on the contrary, be aggravated to the point of detachment of part of the bone (Ytrehus *et al.* 2007: 429-448; McCoy *et al.* 2013: 1638-1647). Some authors consider that the physical stress could be triggered by the animal's own weight upon different skeletal points in conditions of reduced mobility (Weeren/Barneveld 1999: 16-25; Sewell 2010: 1-60). An example of the latter would be stabling. Some wild species of animals studied have also shown signs of having suffered from this pathology (Thompson *et al.* 1994: 137-143; Murray *et al.* 1999: 878-880; Handeland/Bernhoft 2004: 676; Etterlin *et al.* 2017: 445-456). Based on these results, and seeing the need to deepen this line of research, in this work we provide a reference of the development of this pathology in wild populations of roe deer and red deer, with the main objective of providing a reference for the archaeozoology of the skeletal state under natural living conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The bone studied in this research is the astragalus. It has been decided to analyse this bone because of its good level of preservation compared to other bone remains found in archaeological sites, and because the individuals that reach the adult stage maintain practically the same bone size (Albarella/Payne 2005: 589-599; Rowley-Conwy *et al.* 2012: 1-44). Additionally, this bone shows diagnostic morphological characteristics that ease their taxonomic classification. The wild animal species that are part of this collection of reference are the red deer (*Cervus elaphus*) and the roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*). They are species that in areas with a very marked seasonality may have a mobility linked to it (Kropil *et al.* 2015: 63-72; Putman/Werner 2011: 277-291). Another important criterion for the selection of species is the size of the animals, at both interspecific and intraspecific levels. Some studies have been conducted correlating the weight of the animal and the severity of the pathology (Nakano *et al.* 1987: 883-901; Ytrehus *et al.* 2007: 429-448; Ekman/Carlson 1998: 17-32). Most of them conclude that there is no direct relationship between these two variables. The reference collection includes a total of 46 astragalus, 32 roe deer and 14 red deer. These animals were hunted in the province of Girona in 2020. The age, sex, geographical area in which they were hunted and the weight of the individual have been recorded for each animal. The red deer represented in the collection are aged between 8 and 20 months (n=3), between 20 and 32 months (n=6) and over 32 months (n=5). The weight ranges from 48.4 to 133.3 kg. In the case of roe deer, all individuals represented are females between 8 and 15 months of age (n=13) and older than 16 months (n=19). The weight ranges from 13.2 kg in the youngest animals to 26.4 kg in the adults.

A detailed examination of the articular surface of the astragalus was first carried out. If the presence of *osteocondritis* was identified, the morphology, depth, the area occupied by the surface affected by the lesion and the maximum length and width of this area were systematically recorded to characterize its conformation (Zimmerman *et al.* 2018: 13-27; Ruiz 2019: 1-144). It is a pathology that has been described on numerous occasions on the basis of the morphology it presents (Ekman/Carlson 1988: 17-32; Boado/López-Sanromán 2016: 112-117). In this work, a total of four morphological classes are used for classification, three of which correspond to those proposed in the work of Zimmerman *et al.* (2018) (M1=closed circular; M2=open circular with narrow neck and M3=open with wide neck). To these we have added a fourth category (M4) to differentiate those with a height that does not exceed half the trochlea from those that do, which would be classified as M3 (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Representative examples of the different stages of severity in this pathology on red deer at the top and on roe deer at the bottom. It is found gradually from the left, those slighter and on the right more severe. In the first row: M1P1, M1P3, M2P2 and M4P3. In the second row: M1P1, M2P3, M3P3 y M4P4.

Four levels have been described for depth, which are: P1= superficial; P2= shallow; P3= deep and P4= very deep. Once these qualitative characteristics have been determined, we measured the area of the bone surface affected by the lesion. This has been established by delimiting the area with cavity and/or porosity. We used the program ImageJ Fiji. For each of these aspects, descriptive statistical parameters were calculated as a basis for establishing variability and for comparison between species. For the correlation between the size of the animal and the presence of pathology, principal component analysis was used from the database of GLI, GLm, DI, Dm and Bd measurements taken according to the criteria published by von den Driesch (1976).

RESULTS

Of all the astragali analysed, 71.74% had an area affected by *osteochondritis*, being more common in roe deer (81.2%) than in red deer (50%). In the case of roe deer, there was more involvement on the left side (n=17) than on the right (n=9). The predominant morphological category is the second one (M2), detected in 11 specimens (42.31%). This is followed, in order of quantitative importance, by category 4 (n=7), category 1 (n=5) and finally category 3 (n=3). These are, therefore, generally slight affectations. There is no direct

correlation between the type of damage and its depth, although more severe damage tends to be deeper in general. Depth is generally shallow, with 42.31% at level P2. Only 7.69% have reached the most severe depth level (P4). The mean area is 6.67 mm², ranging from 1.3 to 17.8, with a standard deviation of 4.13. There is no correlation between the area of the pathology and the weight of the animal (Fig. 2a), although there is a tendency for smaller animals to be more affected (Fig. 3a).

Regarding the astragalus of red deer with *osteochondritis*, the affectations are relatively slight than in roe deer (Fig. 1). The most represented morphological category is the first one, with 71.43%. Categories 3 and 4 are not represented. The depth parameter shows a similar dynamic, with 42.86% at the P2 level, and no astragalus with severe affectation. The area of this species has a mean of 8,73 mm² and a standard deviation of 5,48. No correlation is observed with weight (Fig. 2b) and size of the animal (Fig. 3b), although for weight it is worth mentioning that the number of specimens for which data on this variable were available is very small.

DISCUSSION

From the studied sample, we can establish that the two wild species have a high representation of individ-

Figure 2. Relation between weight, age and area occupied by the pathology in roe deer (a) and red deer (b).

Figure 3. Correlation between animal size and presence/absence of osteochondritis in roe deer (a) and red deer (b).

uals with pathology, although this is characterized by having a small affected area and low degree of depth, which could be related to a slight type of affectation. Interestingly, it is observed that the two wild species show a differential development of *osteochondritis*, with a tendency to present a more intense affectation in the roe deer, species with a smaller size. This may be related to the increased density of this bone in larger animals (Kreutzer 1992: 271-294; Lyman 1992: 7-22; Ioannidou 2003: 355-365), resulting in greater resistance to physical stress. While in roe deer the M2 developmental stage dominates (42'31%), in red deer the most represented is the slight M1 (71'43%).

With regard to the depth of the affected area, there is high variability, although the traumatism correspond mainly to level 2, being generally not very deep. Regarding the relative area of bone affected, the values obtained, once weighted by the size of the animal, are however similar for the two species. The available bibliography on this aspect has focused mainly on horses, pigs and dogs, species that, in general, have a greater economic impact at present. This does not allow us to make cross-species comparisons from previous studies. One aspect to be noted is that in horses, which are larger, and especially in horses used for racing, the pathology is located in the extremities. In contrast, in pigs and dogs, smaller spe-

cies, the pathology is recorded in various elements of the skeleton (Nakano *et al.* 1979: 491-502); (Ytrehus *et al.* 2004: 188-195; Etterlin *et al.* 2017: 445-456). In addition to the size of the animal, another variable that could be correlated with the dimensions of the affected area may be the weight of the animal. In this case, and in agreement with several authors (Nakano *et al.* 1979: 491-502; Ytrehus *et al.* 2004: 188-195), it has been found that the conformation and condition of the area affected by *osteochondritis* is not always directly correlated with weight. The trend observed for roe deer could be conditioned by the fact that all the animals analyzed are females. In the studies that have been carried out taking this parameter into account, however, no differences between both sexes within the same species have been observed. (Hoppe 1984: 425-429; Nakano *et al.* 1987: 883-901; Zimmermann *et al.* 2018: 13-27). It has also been noted that castrated animals are more susceptible to the development of *osteochondritis* (Hill *et al.* 1998: 171-175).

Some authors proposed that the growth rate can influence the development of *osteochondritis* (Nakano *et al.* 1979: 491-502; Ekman/Carlson 1988: 17-32; Ytrehus *et al.* 2007: 429-448). By relating the age intervals represented by red deer and roe deer, it has been observed that the pathology has a similar affection in different ages. Sewell (2010) raises the question of whether a relatively faster rate of growth or weight gain in domestic animals could be a major causal factor for the presence of *osteochondritis*. In the case of domestic animals, this factor could indicate when the intensity of livestock activities increases. Thus, in farming economies, in some cases the presence of this pathology could be related to rapid weight gain and more controlled meat production. Sewell (2010) notes that although growth rate is not the main cause of *osteochondritis* formation, it is a factor that potentially influences its prevalence.

Because *osteochondrosis* is a pathology that affects growing animals, there is a possibility that the lesions will heal or decrease in severity over time. In the primary stages it develops in the cartilage so that if early healing is assisted it will not be visible on the bone tissue. René van Weeren (2006) has found that the ages at which lesions originate and the ages at which they become undetectable vary for each joint. In the astragalus, for example, lesions that had developed in horses during the first months of life had become undetectable by 5 months of age. The same author characterizes this lesion as dynamic rather than static. Lesions that occur later in life or affect a large surface area are more difficult to repair. The presence of slight affectations in the wild population of the present study could therefore be related to a natural metabolic activity of the articular cartilage in infantile and juvenile age, without detecting mechanical stress.

Biomechanical stress experienced by the animal when performing specific activities has also been related to the development of *osteochondritis*. It is mainly studied in racehorses (Jeffcott 1996: 331-338; Dik/Van Weeren 1999: 9-15), but could also result from their use for traction or transport, among other causes. The astragalus is directly involved in movement and, therefore, is potentially representative of the intensity and form of movement experienced by the animals. However, the lack of mobility can have the same consequences, with severe limitations. When the animal does not move, all the force of the animal's hindquarters is concentrated in the tibia, with its maximum in the distal part (Schaeffer 1947: 1-24). This causes all this weight to be centered on the medial part of the astragalus, which is where the affection is located in most of the cases studied. When the animal is moving or in action, this force also exists, but it is distributed over the entire ridge of the trochlea, as it is a highly mobile joint (Barr 2014: 1201-1216). Consequently, animals that have had less movement throughout their lives may be more severely affected and vice versa (Nakano/Aherne 1988: 154-155; Barak *et al.* 2011: 1141-1151). In this line, the *osteochondritis* has been used in zooarchaeological studies as a pathology indicative of artificial control of animals (Zimmermann *et al.* 2018: 13-27), highlighting the fact that confined animals (both domestic and captive) in small enclosures exhibit high load levels. Sewell (2010) also notes that sheep that have lived outdoors show less evidence of the presence of this pathology compared to other animals that have lived in confinement. Therefore, studying the prevalence of this condition in a population can help us to contrast the degree of activity, mobility or physical stress in general.

CONCLUSION

The present study has provided data on the development of *osteochondritis* in two wild species that have lived within their usual ecological niche. This allows us to understand how this pathology develops when there is no direct anthropic pressure, constituting a reference that can be of great help for the recognition of animal mobility patterns or biomechanical stress from archaeological faunal remains. In this case, it has been detected that, in wild cervid populations, it generally presents a slight development that does not worsen with age, in contrast it has been evidenced in domestic herds managed directly by human communities.

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